

National Technical University of Athens

**School of Electrical and
Computer Engineering**

The Institution aims to address existing gender imbalances in its academic, research and administrative activities. The ECE's priority is to establish a well-adapted Gender Equality Plan, to support structural change through improved procedures, policies, and organisational structures.

Gender Equality Status Analysis

An extensive assessment of **gender bias** and **inequalities** both inside the Institution and in the external Innovation Ecosystem where it is positioned.

This research has been carried out by ECE - NTUA in the context of CALIPER project through the funded European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 873134.

Status of Gender Equality inside the Institution

The internal assessment followed the **three ERA priorities on Gender Equality*** and examined them in the context of **specific activity/service areas** inside ECE - NTUA BA through the collection of qualitative and quantitative data.

The data collection was conducted by the institution researchers, through **desk research, policy analysis, interviews, surveys** and **focus groups**.

Key Findings

HUMAN RESOURCES

The staff of the Institution is mainly composed by **male academics** across the different grades (A, B, C) and **male personnel** with a permanent or temporary contract. The only exception concerns the laboratory and technical staff, which is gender-balanced, while **in administrative positions, women are the majority**.

Sex ratio on type of contract for academics

Permanent: 93% Men 7% Women

Temporary / Fixed Term: Men 82% Women 18%

In the context of recruitment procedures, ECE - NTUA doesn't **have specific gender-sensitive protocols**. It applies the relevant legislations of the Ministry of Education and the Supreme Council for Civil Personnel Selection (ASEP), which do not apply gender-sensitive criteria.

*Council of the European Union (2015). Conclusions on advancing Gender Equality in the European Research Area. RECH 295, COMPET 551, SOC 703

Status of Gender Equality inside the Institution

The Glass Ceiling Index has been **decreasing during the recent years**. In 2017 it was 2.0, in 2018 1,66 and in 2019 still 1,66.

In terms of work-life balance, mainly women are taking parental leaves and the unpaid leave is the most common request, when it comes to long term leaves. As for the remuneration, **the gender pay gap is 68% for all Staff categories**.

INSTITUTIONAL GOVERNANCE

Gender equality is indirectly monitored through statistical data that ECE-NTUA provides to the Ministry of Education and other public organisations, including gender disaggregated data about students populations.

In ECE-NTUA, there are **no specific target quotas/gender quotas** to be applied in the appointment process to leadership positions as well as in the elections to decision making positions/governing bodies. The gender composition in most of the decision-making bodies is **male dominated**.

Gendered Composition of decision making bodies

Deanery (Vice Deans)

80%	20%
Men	Women

General Assembly

92,06%	7,94%
Men	Women

Instruments, Expendables and Services reception Committee (State Budget)

83,33%	16,67%
Men	Women

Instruments, Expendables and Services reception Committee (Research Fund Account)

83,33%	16,67%
Men	Women

Status of Gender Equality inside the Institution

Mentoring or coaching services/activities for leadership positions dedicated to women are not in place.

The Institution doesn't have any Diversity/Equality bodies. However, the Liaison–Student Services Office has undertaken plenty of the responsibilities that such a Body would have.

NTUA created a Committee for Gender Equality (CGE) in 2021 and has held its first meeting on January 14, 2021.

RESEARCH & TEACHING

There is **no current formalised practice** ensuring the integration of the gender dimension into research in a systematic way.

Specific policies or guidelines for the integration of the gender dimension in the curriculum at the School of Electrical and Computer Engineering are not in place.

Currently, there are no formal guidelines for gender-sensitive teaching in the Greek legislation or within the Institution. However, the legislative framework for the promotion of gender equality through education and learning exists.

STUDENT SERVICES

In the context of NTUA and the School of Electrical and Computer Engineering, several services are provided to students, including a career counselling office and a psychological support service.

All these services aim at giving advice and counselling at enrolled students regarding any kind of matter, including gender equality issues. However, **it is not clear a gender-sensitive approach is adopted.**

Status of Gender Equality inside the Institution

TRANSFER TO MARKET

The Institution produces several and substantial research results, which it transfers to the market through scientific paper and theses.

However, there is a well-documented gap between female and male participants as speakers to STEM conferences.

Average gender ratio of professors participating in STEM conferences on STEM in the last 3 years

The NTUA Innovation and Entrepreneurship Unit provides support to student-led start-ups. At the moment there are **no gender disaggregated data available concerning start-ups.**

INTERSECTIONALITY

In order to prevent intersectionality-related issues, NTUA applies the national Law 3896/ 2010 (Official Government Gazette, 2010) and has taken actions in particular on disability issues. Such actions mainly concern scholarship programs to students, infrastructural accessibility improvement, and psychological support.

However, there is space of improvement on tackling the issue and, in particular, on how disability intersects with gender and other discrimination grounds as well as on improving the dissemination of the existing measures.

The complete report is publicly available [here](#).

Status of Gender Equality in the Innovation Ecosystem

The first part of the external assessment included an analysis of the **national legal and policy framework**. The second, focused on the **National and Regional Innovation Ecosystems**. A **context analysis** was implemented through a dedicated desk research and complemented with interviews with internal stakeholders. In addition to the context analysis, a **mapping** was conducted by ECE - NTUA to identify existing and potential synergies with external stakeholders. The mapping included a focus group with internal stakeholders, a survey for external stakeholders and a Social Network Analysis.

Key Findings

NATIONAL LEGAL AND POLICY FRAMEWORK

The equality between men and women is stated in the Greek Constitution.

Greek State has established legislative procedures and policies to promote gender equality like the **Family Law reform of 1983** and the more recent **Greek Strategy for Gender Equality 2016-2020 (GSGE)** and **Law 4606/2019** providing the content of **Equality Plans** and provisions about **gender sensitive budgeting**.

Law 4589/2019 foresees the establishment of a Committee for Gender Equality in each University.

Gender quotas in decision-making bodies are established by **Law 4386/2016**, which states that each gender should be represented **by at least 1/3 of the committee members** in evaluation and selection committees and advisory bodies in the field of research, technology and innovation.

Status of Gender Equality in the Innovation Ecosystem

ANALYSIS OF NATIONAL INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS

The most recent data about STEM High School and Higher Education students show that **less than one third of STEM students are female**.

The share of female STEM researchers is slightly more positive (38%), while the evolution of the employment rate in R&D from 2011 to 2017, does not show any relevant progress in the mentioned period, since the female share only increased of about 1% (from 36.71% to 37.82%).

The presence of women in patent registration teams is overall **limited**.

Also, the percentage of female founders and leaders of start-ups is very low.

Start-up founders ratio per gender

The level of integration of gender as a scientific research dimension is not monitored and no documents were identified exploring the integration of gender in product or service development.

SOCIAL NETWORK ANALYSIS

The Institution has various partnerships in place with universities, ICT companies, NGOs and public government bodies.

Status of Gender Equality in the Innovation Ecosystem

Gender inequalities are only partially perceived by the stakeholders involved in the present research, although notable mitigation actions that have been identified include equality committees and “gender laboratories”, quotas in decision making bodies, and adoption of specific measures for fostering work-life balance.

The Analysis of ECE-NTUA identified **89 stakeholders** most of them belonging to the Industry & Business sector.

Almost half of the collaborations have a **female leadership**, even though they refer to only six women, who oversee the majority of collaborations with the industry sector. Eleven collaborations focus on gender issues, most of them with Civil Society stakeholders.

The complete report is publicly available [here](#).

This research has been conducted in the context of Horizon 2020 project, CALIPER.

The results will be used for the project's next implementation phases.

ECE - NTUA is one of the 9 Research Organisations across Europe which participates in CALIPER to develop a **Gender Equality Plan (GEP)** and engage the local Innovation Hubs to transfer the gained knowledge beyond academia.

Discover more about CALIPER

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